

Assessing the changing relationship between the No.11 sugar price and WTI oil price with structural breaks and Vector Error Correction models

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Abstract: Owing to the use of sugar in production of ethanol, which can be used as an alternative fuel source, the oil and sugar price show correlation. This dissertation aims to explore the long-run relationship between the No.11 sugar price and WTI oil price and how this has changed across four different sub-periods. This dissertation uses several econometric techniques, namely the Bai-Perron (1998) structural breaks test, Engle-Granger (1987) cointegration test, and subsequent vector error correction models. The data covers the period March 2003 to February 2023 and is split into four sub-periods within this for comparison. The empirical results indicate no long-run relationship in the first two sub-periods (2003 to 2006 and 2006 to 2010) and then a significant long-run relationship in the final two (2010 to 2017 and 2017 to 2023), with changes in the oil price having a larger impact on the long-run equilibrium than changes in the sugar price.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

The current energy price crisis highlights the need for alternative fuel sources. One such source is energy produced from biofuels, particularly ethanol, in the production of which Brazil is a world leader (Renewable fuels association, 2021). While ethanol cars have been in circulation in Brazil since 1975, 2003 saw the introduction of flex-fuel vehicles (FFV) which can run on hydrous ethanol, gasoline, or a mixture (Cruz, et al., 2014). In 2010, FFV's accounted for 81.8% of new registered vehicles (Nascimento, 2014) and this number has stayed high to this day.

Ethanol is an important biofuel which can be produced from different commodities, with Brazil using sugarcane as the main input, although other countries, such as the US, use corn instead (Avalos, 2014). Brazil has an advantage when it comes to producing sugar, with its favourable climate and land availability allowing it to become the largest sugar producing country in the world, accounting for 36.7% of global supply in 2021 (Government of Brazil, 2022). However, these large levels of sugar production leaves Brazil with excess sugar after the domestic market has been supplied. Therefore, Brazil welcomes the use of excess sugar for ethanol production as it prevents the need to export to the world market at a lower price compared to domestic trade. Not only this, but biofuels produce lower amounts of greenhouse gases compared to fossil fuels (Jia, et al., 2017), as well as being a source of renewable energy, which is better for the environment and longevity of the planet as a habitable atmosphere.

While ethanol has many advantages, it does not currently capture the entire fuel market in Brazil, instead it is shared with gasoline which can also be used in FFVs, with 24.4 billion litres of domestic ethanol consumption in 2010 compared to 22.7 billion litres of gasoline that same year (Nuñez & Otero, 2017, p. 2). The main input for gasoline is oil, so while the ethanol price is linked to the raw sugar price, the gasoline price is linked to the global crude oil price (Nuñez & Otero, 2017). As both ethanol and gasoline can be used to fuel vehicles, the sugar and oil prices are also strongly interlinked. When the global sugar price is high, ethanol becomes more expensive and, if the cost at the pump for ethanol crosses a threshold above 70% of the gasoline price, consumers rationally choose to use petrol (Pacini, et al., 2013), and vice versa. Hypothetically, this should cause the sugar price to adjust downwards to meet the

lower demand, however the data suggests otherwise, see Figure 1, as the oil and sugar prices are not constantly adjusting to reach a long-run equilibrium.

Figure 1 – WTI Oil and No.11 Sugar prices 2003 to 2023 (Source: UK Investing, 2023)

Therefore, there must be other factors influencing the prices which prevent this equilibrium from occurring. These factors might include global economic crises, supply issues, etc. Despite not being directly related, it is important to see how changes in the oil market impact the sugar market, and vice versa, as this information is useful to investors and policymakers in both markets. It is also useful to see how the relationship has changed over time since the introduction of FFV's in Brazil in 2003 so investors and policymakers can better forecast their respective prices and see how changes in policies or events in one market may impact the other. To explore this, I split the data into four sub-periods between March 2003 and February 2023 based on structural break testing. Following the splitting of data, I used a Vector Error Correction model (VECM) to assess the relationship between the No.11 sugar price and WTI (West Texas Intermediate) oil price in each sub-period, as VECM provides both short run dynamics and the long-run relationship between the series being studied.

The next stage of this dissertation reviews the existing literature on cointegrating relationships and VECM's with a focus on commodity markets. I then outline the data series being analysed and the methodology used to prepare the data for analysis using VECM, as well as diagnostic testing to see how well the model fits. I then analyse the

results from the VECM in each sub-period and provide a conclusion based on the findings.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

This chapter reviews the existing literature surrounding the different econometric techniques used in this dissertation as well as their applications. Particularly, it will focus on cointegration, Vector Error Correction Models, Vector Autoregressive Models, and structural breaks and how these combined can help assess relationships in stock and commodity markets.

2.1. Definitions

The idea of cointegration was developed by Engle and Granger (1987) who formally define it as “The components of the vector x_t are said to be co-integrated order d, b , denoted $x_t \sim CI(d, b)$, if (i) all components of x_t are $I(d)$; (ii) there exists a vector $a (\neq 0)$ so that $z_t = a'x_t - I(d - b), b > 0$. The vector a is called the co-integrating vector.” (Engle & Granger, 1987, p. 253). In other words, cointegration shows whether there is a long-run relationship between the means of the variables being studied. There are three main methods to study the existence of cointegration, the Engle-Granger Two-step method (Engle & Granger, 1987), the Johansen test (Johansen, 1991), and the Phillips-Ouliaris test (Phillips & Ouliaris, 1988). The different tests have benefits and drawbacks depending on the variables being studied. The Engle-Granger method, the first to be developed, is commonly used due its simplicity, however this simplicity can be its limitation as if there are more than two variables being studied, it may result in more than two cointegration relationships. These limitations have been improved upon in later methods such as the Johansen test which allows for testing of multiple cointegrating vectors. Though while this improvement is welcomed, it is usually recommended that both tests be performed for completeness as the Engle-Granger test is generally more robust (Gonzalo & Lee, 1998). Many studies use cointegration to explore economic relationships, such as using the Engle-Granger test to find the relationship between nominal interest rates and inflation (MacDonald & Murphy, 1989) or the relationship between stock prices and exchange rates (Abidin, et al., 2013)

and (Muhammad, et al., 2002). Muhammad et al. primarily use the Johansen test with the Engle-Granger test confirming their findings.

To extend the analysis on cointegration, a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) can be used to determine the long-run relationship and direction of causality should there be cointegration between the variables. VECM's are cointegrated Vector Autoregressive (VAR) models. VAR models were first developed by Christopher Sims (1980) but had some problems, namely when variables were cointegrated or the error terms were not stationary. This led to the development of the Vector Error Correction Model which allows for these occurrences. There are many studies which use VECM to assess long term relationships, particularly of stocks markets, such as of Singapore's stock market (Maysami & Koh, 2000) or among G7 countries (Menezes, et al., 2012). Others examine the more complicated relationships such as between interest rate and inflation towards exchange rate volatility in Malaysia (Asari, et al., 2011).

The next section focusses on exploring how different studies use VECM and VAR models to assess relationships between commodity prices. There are not many studies which look specifically into only the oil and sugar prices, so I have classified the literature based on the methodology used.

2.2. Research Studies based on simple VECM

Combining these techniques and the occasional less traditional method, such as Detrended Partial-Cross-Correlation Analysis (DPCCA), there are more specific studies which relate to commodity and oil prices. Chaudhuri (2001) explored the long-run relationship between world primary commodity prices and the oil price, over 1973 to 1996, by first using the Engle-Granger cointegration test. Chaudhuri found cointegration existed in 20 out of 22 cases at a 10% significance level. Chaudhuri then used a VECM to test for causality and found changes in the oil price cause changes in commodity prices, but not vice versa.

Balcombe and Rapsomanikis (2008) analysed the sugar-ethanol-oil nexus in Brazil from 2000 to 2006 using a Bayesian Monte Carlo Markov Chain and a threshold vector error correction model (TVECM). They used this Bayesian approach as it can deal with the volatility of the commodity market, as well as removing errors that may be made from prematurely deciding the cointegrating rank. Bayesian estimation in this case allowed

Balcombe and Rapsomanikis to calculate the marginal likelihood so they could compare a range of nonnested specifications. It also meant they could choose lag length, select rank restrictions, and test for weak and strong exogeneity. The use of a TVECM instead of a simple VECM was useful in helping find the threshold above or below which the relationships change, as commodity markets can present non-linear effects, though TVECM's assume constant cointegration relations among prices which can cause bias in the model. Balcombe and Rapsomanikis concluded the long-run equilibria of sugar and ethanol prices were determined by oil prices.

Lima et al. (2019) extended the work of Balcombe and Rapsomanikis (2008) by using a recently introduced method of cross-correlation, the DPCCA coefficient, to investigate the relationship between the Brazilian energy and food market – specifically ethanol and sugar over a longer period 2000 to 2016. They used this method due to its ability to deal with more complex relations compared with simple cointegration. The Brazilian energy (ethanol) and food (sugar) markets are overly complex as they are both influenced by multiple external factors such as crude oil prices or Brazilian economic development. This means Detrended Cross-Correlation Analysis (DCCA) cannot be used by itself, hence the use of DPCCA here to reveal long-term power-law cross correlations. Lima et al. (2019, p. 692) discovered that “the diversion of sugar cane for biofuel production (due to the variations in ethanol prices), affects more sugar prices than the price movements in external energy market”.

Carpio (2019) expanded on both Lima et al. (2019) and Balcombe & Rapsomanikis (2008) through the inclusion of gasoline prices when studying the effects of oil price volatility. Carpio studied the impact of world oil prices on Brazilian ethanol and gasoline, and world sugar price forecasts using data from 2001 to 2018. Carpio used the Johansen test and found cointegration between all four. Subsequently, Carpio used a VECM to find in the short-term, changes in the oil price had less of an effect on the price of sugar than the price of ethanol and gasoline.

The next section extends these studies to include structural breaks as the relationship between different commodity prices change over time.

2.3. Research Studies based on VECM with Structural Breaks

While most literature simply studies relationships over a set period of time, Chen and Saghaian (2015) introduce the possibility of structural breaks in the data. A structural break occurs when we see a change in the parameters of a model. For price series affected by exogenous variables, for example the oil price, global economic events, such as the 2008 financial crash, can cause changes in the long-run means of the prices. These breaks can be tested for using the Chow test (Chow, 1960) if breakpoints are known, or the Quandt likelihood ratio (QLR) statistic if breakpoints are unknown (Quandt, 1960). Bai and Perron (1998) extended these previous methodologies to include the ability to test for multiple break points by using a sup Wald type test with the null hypothesis of no change and the alternative with an arbitrary number of changes.

Some studies explore the change in relationships before and after structural breaks. Avalos (2014) studied the connection between US oil, corn, and soybean prices over the period January 1986 to April 2012, with corn being the main input of ethanol production in the US, and soybean being a competing, alternative crop to corn. Avalos's main hypothesis was that there is a structural break in or around May 2006 due to the introduction of the 2005 Energy Policy Act which meant the oil prices became a relevant part of the corn market and as such changes in the oil price will have a stronger effect on the corn prices after May 2006. To verify the existence of this structural break, they used Chow tests, both sample split and breakpoint, as they had no normality of disturbances as they were only white noise processes with an id distribution. Following this, Avalos used a bilateral Johansen test to test for cointegration in the sub-period after the structural break (May 2006 to April 2012) and found that soybean and corn prices were no longer stationary and that oil and corn prices were now cointegrated when they were not prior to May 2006.

Chen and Saghaian (2015) conducted a similar study by using a Perron Unit Root test to determine the breakpoints in the data, settling on Week 1 2009 as it fell within the break points discovered in each of the three price series they studied (oil, ethanol, and sugar). Chen and Saghaian then used the Johansen test and discovered no long-run relationship between the prices within the first sub-period (Week 21 2003 to Week 52 2008). Following this, they used a VAR model and Granger causality tests to find that the oil price Granger caused the sugar and ethanol price during the first sub-period. In

the second period (Week 1 2009 to Week 35 2014), Chen and Saghaian found one cointegration relationship so were able to use a VECM to determine the direction of interaction. They found the oil price makes longer term changes in the other two prices compared to the first period which was more short term.

Following Chen and Saghaian's (2015) investigation using structural breaks, I extended the period of interest to 2003 to 2023, as well as only investigating the simpler relationship between the No.11 sugar price and WTI oil price. These relationships appear strongly correlated with each other partly because of Brazil's FFV's. However, as this scheme is relatively new, I believe the relationship has become stronger over time. Therefore, I use Bai and Perron (1998) methodology to determine structural break points, of which I expected there to be multiple due to the longer period being studied, before studying for cointegration, and using a VECM once cointegration was found to assess their long-run equilibrium relationship to help inform policymakers and investors better about how events in the two markets might impact each other.

Chapter 3: Methodology chapter

This chapter outlines the methodology used to investigate if there is a long-run relationship between the No.11 sugar and WTI oil prices. To begin to explore their relationship, I first assessed the stationarity of the full time series using an Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test to help select appropriate methodology. If they were not stationary, the natural logarithm of the data is taken and if stationarity persists the first logarithmic difference was taken so they were both integrated of order $I(1)$. Following these tests, I followed the Bai and Perron (1998) structural break methodology to find the number of break points in the data and their locations. This allowed me to split the data into the different sub-periods and so see how the relationship between the prices has changed between these periods. This gives an insight into reasons why the relationship between the two price series may follow more (or less) closely and gives an insight to investors and policymakers as to how changes in one market may impact the other following economic events, and vice versa. Following this, I tested for cointegration between the two price series in each sub-period, and subsequently estimated a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) to assess the short-run dynamics and long-run relationship between the oil and sugar price.

3.1 Structural Breaks

Structural breaks are common in long time series due to outside factors affecting the parameters of the data. When structural breaks are present, they can create bias in the subsequent model estimation. Therefore, to bypass the need for a threshold vector error correction model which assumes constant cointegration relations among prices, I followed Mohanty and Langley (2003) and Chen and Saghaian (2015) by first finding the structural break points and splitting the data into sub-periods based on this prior to model estimation. Bai and Perron (1998) introduced the idea of structural break testing and proposed three different tests to test for and estimate points of structural change.

The test used in this dissertation was estimated in Stata using the **xtbreak** command (Ditzen, et al., 2021) which uses Bai and Perron (1998) methodology, in particular the hypothesis no breaks vs s breaks. This hypothesis was used as the number and location of breakpoints can be estimated by observing the data. To assess this hypothesis, the Chow (1960) test is used. More specifically, the F-statistic is estimated based on Equation 1, with critical values chosen from the F-distribution with s numerator degrees of freedom and $N(T - p - (s + 1)q) - p - (s + 1)q$ denominator degrees of freedom. If the F-statistic is smaller than these critical values then the null hypothesis of no structural breaks cannot be rejected, however if it is larger in absolute value, I can reject the null and accept the alternative of s breaks.

Equation 1 – Chow test F-statistic

$$y_{i,t} = x'_{i,t}\beta + w'_{i,t}\delta_j + f'_t\gamma_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Where $t = T_{j-1}, \dots, T_j$ and $j = 1, \dots, s + 1$ with $T_0 = 0$ and $T_{s+1} = T$. There are s breaks.

$y_{i,t}$ is the dependant variable, and $x_{i,t}$ and $w_{i,t}$ are $p \times 1$ and $q \times 1$ vectors of regressors, respectively. $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ is the error term and is assumed to be independent of the regressors, f_t an $m \times 1$ vector of factors and γ_i a conformable vector of factor loadings.

If the set of break dates, $\mathcal{J}_{s,\epsilon}$ is unknown, the supremum statistic is used:

Equation 2 – Supreme statistic

$$\sup F(s) = \sup_{\mathcal{J}_s \in \mathcal{J}_{s,\epsilon}} F(\mathcal{J}_s)$$

Where,

Equation 3 – Set of allowed break dates

$$\mathcal{T}_{s,\epsilon} = \left\{ (T_1, \dots, T_s) : T_{j+1} - T_j \geq \epsilon T, T_1 \geq \epsilon T, T_s \leq (1 - \epsilon) T \right\}$$

is the set of allowed break dates with the trimming parameter, $\epsilon = 0.15$, to exclude the top and bottom 15% of observations prior to testing to reduce the influence of anomalies on the data.

3.2 Cointegration

Following the splitting of the data into the found sub-periods, I again assessed stationarity of each sub-period using an ADF test to make sure the data is ready for analysis. To test for cointegration, I used Engle-Granger (1987) methodology. While the Engle-Granger (1987) test has some drawbacks as it is sensitive to which variable is used on the left-hand side of the equation, this can be overcome in a two-variable system by conducting the test with both oil and sugar on the left-hand side in subsequent tests.

Engle and Granger (1987, p. 253) describe cointegration in the following way “The components of the vector x_t are said to be co-integrated order d, b , denoted $x_t \sim CI(d, b)$, if (i) all components of x_t are $I(d)$; (ii) there exists a vector $a (\neq 0)$ so that $z_t = a'x_t - I(d - b), b > 0$. The vector a is called the co-integrating vector.” This shows whether there is a long-run relationship between the means of the variables being studied.

For two non-stationary variables (of same order of integration, e.g., $I(1)$) and the model $Y_t = \alpha + \beta X_t + u_t$, there is cointegration between Y_t and X_t if the residuals are stationary (i.e., $u_t \sim I(0)$). Based on this, the Engle-Granger (1987) test involves estimating the regression model $Y_t = \alpha + \beta X_t + u_t$ and testing the regression residuals \widehat{u}_t for the presence of a unit root using an ADF test. This involves estimating the equation $\Delta \widehat{u}_t = c + \gamma_1 \Delta \widehat{u}_{t-1} + \dots + \gamma_N \Delta \widehat{u}_{t-N} + \epsilon_t$ and testing the hypotheses:

$$H_0: \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_N \geq 0$$

$$H_1: \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_N < 0$$

Where the null suggests no cointegration and the alternative implies cointegration exists. If the test statistic estimated is greater than the Engle and Yoo (1987) critical values, then the null hypothesis can be rejected, thus suggesting cointegration exists.

The number of lags was chosen using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and the resulting ADF test revealed both series were integrated of order I(1). Following the cointegration tests, I ran a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) to discover the long-run and short-run dynamics between the sugar and oil prices.

3.3 Vector Error Correction model

Vector error correction models (VECM) are an extension of a Vector Autoregressive model (VAR) in the case of cointegrated variables (David, et al., 2019). To account for short-run dynamics, VECMs are specified in differences. As well as short-run behaviour, they have error correction terms (ECT) and cointegrating equations to show the adjustments to equilibrium and long-run cointegration relationships. The VECM takes the form:

Equation 4 – VECM

$$\Delta y_t = c + \sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \mu_t + \alpha(\beta' Y_{t-1} - \beta_0)$$

Where c is the intercept, γ a vector which includes the short-run cointegrating vector, α is the adjustment coefficient, β the long-run cointegrating vector and μ_t is the independently and identically distributed (iid) error term.

I used the **vec** command in Stata to create the VECM and included an unrestricted constant trend in the VECM due to both the sugar and oil price data having a linear trend and being stationary around a constant non-zero mean.

3.4 Residual Diagnostics

To check the estimated VECM is suitable, tests for autocorrelation and normality need to be run.

- *Lagrange-Multiplier (Breusch, 1978) (LM) test for autocorrelation*: The LM test tests for autocorrelation in the residuals in the model. Using the **veclmar**

command in Stata, it tests the null of no autocorrelation at lag j versus the alternative of autocorrelation. If the residuals show autocorrelation, the model is unreliable, and the number of lags needs to be increased.

- *Jarque-Bera (Jarque & Bera, 1980) (JB) test for normality*: Using the **vecnorm**, **jbera** command in Stata, the JB test tests for normally distributed residuals, with the null hypothesis of normality versus the alternative of non-normality. If the residuals do not show normality, the parameter estimates will be consistent but not efficient.

Chapter 4: Empirical Findings

This chapter summarises and discusses the empirical results from the structural break testing and VECM tests outlined in Chapter 3. To evaluate the relationship between the oil and sugar price, a four-step procedure has been implemented. Starting with the estimation of structural breaks using the Bai and Perron (1998) method, the second step involves testing for stationarity and unit roots using an ADF test, the third step testing for cointegration using the Engle-Granger (1987) cointegration test, and the final step the estimation of a VECM.

4.1 Data description

To assess the relationship between the sugar and oil price this dissertation uses the weekly averages of the No. 11 raw sugar price (in US cents per lb) and the West Texas Intermediate (WTI) oil price (in US dollars per barrel (bbl)). The No. 11 sugar price has been chosen as it is commonly known as the ‘world benchmark for raw sugar trading’ (ICE, 2022). I used this as opposed to the No. 5 white sugar price as white sugar is generally refined for consumption purposes and not used for ethanol production (Shapouri & Salassi, 2006). I will also be using the WTI Oil price as opposed to the Brent Crude oil price as it is more generally used for gasoline refining and so is seen as the global benchmark for the oil price (CME, 2023), whereas Brent crude is typically a benchmark for oil in the wider market, such as the Middle East, Europe, and Africa.

The total observation period starts from week beginning 2nd March 2003 when FFV’s were first introduced in Brazil, to week beginning 12th February 2023, a total of 1,042

observations, sourced from UK Investing (2023). Following Chen and Saghaian (2015), the data has been split into 4 sub-periods based on the results from structural break testing as outlined in Chapter 3. This dissertation uses **loil**, **lsugar** and **dloil**, **dlsugar** to depict the natural logarithm and first logarithmic difference of each price series respectively. Table 1 contains descriptive statistics of the data for the full time series as well as each sub-period found in the subsequent tests.

Table 1 - Description of data

Period	Obs.	Mean	S.D.	Min	Max	Skew	Kurtosis	Mean	S.D.	Min	Max	Skew	Kurtosis
		oil						sugar					
Full	1,042	68.22	23.70	16.94	145.29	0.35	2.46	15.34	5.48	5.45	33.98	0.67	3.40
1	155	44.58	12.37	25.67	68.35	0.26	1.74	8.53	2.68	5.45	19.30	1.84	7.79
2	213	75.78	22.51	33.87	145.29	1.02	3.88	14.11	4.76	8.56	29.90	1.35	4.09
3	385	76.48	23.74	29.42	113.93	-0.37	1.60	19.04	5.01	10.44	33.98	0.86	3.21
4	289	64.30	19.33	16.94	120.67	0.50	3.51	14.95	3.14	9.73	21.58	0.36	1.75
		loil						lsugar					
Full	1,042	4.16	0.37	2.83	4.98	-0.40	2.70	2.67	0.37	1.70	3.53	-0.30	2.87
1	155	3.76	0.28	3.25	4.22	-0.02	1.66	2.10	0.27	1.70	2.96	1.00	3.91
2	213	4.29	0.28	3.52	4.98	0.17	3.23	2.60	0.30	2.15	3.40	0.84	2.82
3	385	4.28	0.35	3.38	4.74	-0.63	1.98	2.91	0.25	2.35	3.53	0.30	2.64
4	289	4.12	0.32	2.83	4.79	-0.80	4.96	2.68	0.21	2.28	3.07	0.16	1.71

Note: Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the full **oil** and **sugar** time series and four sub-periods (**Full, 1, 2, 3, 4**), as well as the descriptive statistics following their logarithmic transformations (**loil, lsugar**). Both **oil** and **sugar** are in original units, US\$/barrel and US cents/lb respectively. The **mean** shows the average of each price series, **S.D.** the standard deviation from the mean, **min** and **max** the minimum and maximum observations, and **skew** (skewness) and **kurtosis** the third and fourth moments of the data.

4.2 Structural break testing

Observing Figure 1 of the full time series, 12 breakpoints can be identified. However, this needs to be restricted as each sub-period would not have enough observations to produce significant results. Therefore, I focussed on the main breaks and found either 3 or 4 main ones in both the sugar and oil price series. Table 2 summarises the results from testing for a number of structural breaks, with the null hypothesis of no breaks vs s breaks. The test tests the original untransformed series. From Table 2, both 3 and 4 structural breaks are significant to the 1% level for both price series, thus I can reject the null of no structural breaks and instead accept the alternative of 3 or 4 to a 1% level of significance. The dates suggested for 4 breaks are summarised in Table 3.

Table 2 – *xtbreak* test results

	oil	sugar
3 breakpoints	362.42***	684.86***
4 breakpoints	332.32***	544.08***
*** $p < 0.01$. Source: own calculations in Stata		
Note: the null hypothesis is the time series has no structural break, versus the alternative of 3 or 4 breaks respectively. The critical value for 1% level of significance is 7.60 and 6.19 for 3 and 4 breakpoints respectively.		

Table 3 – Breakdates from *xtbreak* test

Breakpoint	oil	sugar	average
1	19/02/2006	19/02/2006	19/02/2006
2	21/11/2010	12/07/2009	17/03/2010
3	02/11/2014	14/10/2012	23/10/2013
4	12/11/2017	23/04/2017	02/08/2017
Source: own calculations in Stata			
Note: these are the predicted break dates for 4 breakpoints suggested by Stata from the same test from Table 1.			

Based on the respective sizes of the first 2 sub-periods and to keep consistency, the last break is in 2017. As, apart from the first break, the sugar and oil break dates are different, an average has been taken between the two. However, the third break is wildly different for both sugar and oil (a 25-month spread) so I disregarded it and used the other three break dates, thus giving 4 sub-periods:

- **2nd March 2003 to 19th February 2006**
- **26th February 2006 to 17th March 2010**
- **24th March 2010 to 2nd August 2017**
- **9th August 2017 to 3rd February 2023**

The first sub-period covers the period from the introduction of flex-fuel vehicles in Brazil to pre-2008 financial crash. The second sub-period covers during and the immediate aftermath of the financial crash, this period is characterised by high volatility and a significant peak and crash in the oil price in July 2008. The third sub-period covers the longer-term aftermath of the crash, with the government and investors being more conservative in investing and policies. The final sub-period covers the most recent 6 years, which include the COVID-19 pandemic and Russian invasion

of Ukraine which have both significantly impacted the oil price in particular. Figure 2 shows the full price series data with the black lines indicating the breakpoints.

Figure 2 - WTI Oil and No.11 Sugar prices 2003 to 2023 split into sub-periods (Source: UK Investing, 2023)

4.3 Stationarity testing

To continue with analysis, the series need to be stationary and integrated of the same order. The original series displays evidence of non-stationarity, so the log and first log difference of each price series has been taken. The results in Table 4 show both transformed price series in all sub-periods are significant to the 1% level, so the null of a unit root was rejected and thus I can conclude the transformed series are stationary.

Table 4 – ADF test

Period	dloil	dlsugar
Full	-31.212***	-32.267***
1	-13.329***	-10.716***
2	-16.497***	-16.237***
3	-17.906***	-19.509***
4	-14.478***	-16.201***

*** $p < 0.01$. Source: own calculations in Stata

Note: These are the test statistics following the ADF test in Stata, with the critical value for 1% level of significance -3.492.

4.4 Cointegration

Table 5 summarises the results from the Engle-Granger (1987) cointegration test, with both oil and sugar tested as the dependant variable. These results suggest the existence of cointegration to a 1% level of significance in all sub-periods being studied. The number of lags was chosen using the Akaike information criterion (AIC) and the results from this are summarised in Table 6.

Table 5 - Engle-Granger cointegration results

Period	oil	sugar
Full	-13.188***	-15.536***
1	-5.947***	-7.826***
2	-15.439***	-6.056***
3	-13.748***	-8.591***
4	-7.517***	-8.506***

*** $p < 0.01$. Source: own calculations in Stata

Note: These are the test statistics following the ADF test on the residuals post regression in Stata, with the critical value for 1% level of significance -3.492. The results for **oil** follow oil being on the left-hand side of the regression, and **sugar** for sugar being on the left-hand side.

Table 6 - VECM lag selection

Lags	AIC	HQIC	SBIC
Sub-period 1			
1	5.204	5.252	5.324*
2	5.187	5.268	5.387
3	5.138	5.251*	5.417
4	5.124*	5.270	5.483
Sub-period 2			
1	8.180*	8.218*	8.276*
2	8.199	8.264	8.359
3	8.206	8.296	8.429
4	8.185	8.302	8.473
Sub-period 3			
1	7.649*	7.674*	7.712*
2	7.661	7.702	7.765
3	7.673	7.730	7.818
4	7.676	7.750	7.862
Sub-period 4			

1	7.050	7.081*	7.127*
2	7.066	7.118	7.194
3	7.056	7.128	7.236
4	7.006*	7.099	7.237

* is the optimal lag selection. Source: own calculations in Stata.

4.5 VECM

Following the discovery of cointegration in all sub-periods and the full time series, I estimated a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) to assess short-run dynamics and the long-run relationship between the sugar and oil prices. I chose the number of lags based off the results in Table 6 using the AIC criteria, increasing the number of lags in the second period to 2 when post-estimation diagnostics indicated autocorrelation. The diagnostic test results following this adjustment of the second period lag are in Table 7 for all sub-periods. Due to the error correction term in the VECM, heteroskedasticity is less of a concern as it helps stabilise the variance of the residuals over time so I did not test for it. While normality is preferred, the non-normal residuals in sub-period 1 can be ignored due to the large number of observations.

Table 7 – VECM diagnostic testing

Period	LM test		Jarque-Bera test		
	Lag 1	Lag 2	d_loil	d_lsugar	ALL
Full	0.290	0.686	0.000	0.000	0.000
1	0.308	0.349	0.399	0.000	0.000
2	0.229	0.232	0.000	0.000	0.000
3	0.167	0.601	0.000	0.000	0.000
4	0.356	0.103	0.000	0.005	0.000

Note: this table shows the results from the diagnostic tests following the VECM for each sub-period and full time series and adjustment of lags to remove autocorrelation. The figures are the prob > chi2 values. For the LM test, the null hypothesis of no autocorrelation cannot be rejected at the 5% level when prob>chi2 > 0.05, and for the Jarque-Bera test, the null hypothesis of non-normality cannot be rejected at the 5% level when prob>chi2 > 0.05.

4.5.1 Sub-period 1

Sub-period 1 covers the period from week beginning 2nd March 2003 to week beginning 19th February 2006. Equations 5 and 6 describe the short-run dynamics and long-run relationship between the oil and sugar prices.

Equation 5

$$\Delta loil_t = 0.007 - 0.126\Delta loil_{t-1} - 0.142\Delta loil_{t-2} + 0.043\Delta lsugar_{t-1} \\ + 0.035\Delta lsugar_{t-2} - 0.018(\Delta loil_{t-1} - 0.148\Delta lsugar_{t-1} - 3.383)$$

Equation 6

$$\Delta lsugar_t = 0.004 + 0.021\Delta loil_{t-1} + 0.036\Delta loil_{t-2} + 0.127\Delta lsugar_{t-1} \\ - 0.271\Delta lsugar_{t-2} + 0.033(\Delta loil_{t-1} - 0.148\Delta lsugar_{t-1} - 3.383)$$

Table 8 – VECM results sub-period 1

Coefficients	Oil	Sugar
ν	0.007*	0.004
γ_1	-0.126*	0.043
γ_2	-0.142*	0.035
θ_1	0.021	0.127
θ_2	0.036	-0.271***
α	-0.018	0.033**
β	1.000	-0.148
β_0	-3.383	-3.383

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$. Source: own calculations

in Stata

The coefficients estimated for Equation 4 (Methodology chapter) from the VECM are summarised in Table 8, with θ_i in place of the cointegrating vector γ_i for the $\Delta lsugar_t$ equation. The adjustment coefficient α_{lsugar} is statistically different from zero to 5% level; however, due to the coefficient sign being positive, there could be movement away from the long-run equilibrium between oil and sugar. In comparison, the sign on the adjustment coefficient α_{loil} is negative, suggesting adjustment towards the equilibrium in the long-run. However, neither of the adjustment coefficients are both negative and statistically significant, suggesting no long-run relationship between the sugar and oil prices in the first sub-period. This could be the result of the relatively recent introduction of FFV's not creating significant correlation between the two markets.

4.5.2 Sub-period 2

Sub-period 2 covers the period from week beginning 26th February 2006 to week beginning 17th March 2010. Equations 7 and 8 describe the short-run dynamics and long-run relationship between the oil and sugar prices.

Equation 7

$$\Delta loil_t = -0.074\Delta loil_{t-1} - 0.150\Delta lsugar_{t-1} - 0.022(\Delta loil_{t-1} - 0.161\Delta lsugar_{t-1} - 3.929)$$

Equation 8

$$\Delta lsugar_t = -0.050\Delta loil_{t-1} - 0.094\Delta lsugar_{t-1} - 0.006(\Delta loil_{t-1} - 0.161\Delta lsugar_{t-1} - 3.929)$$

Table 9 – VECM results sub-period 2

Coefficients	Oil	Sugar
ν	0.000	0.000
γ_1	-0.074	-0.150*
θ_1	-0.050	-0.094
α	-0.022	-0.006
β	1.000	-0.161
β_0	-3.929	-3.929

* $p < 0.1$. Source: own calculations in Stata

Note: the constant ν has been rounded down to 0 for both oil and sugar equations as extremely small values.

The coefficients estimated from the VECM are in Table 9. While both adjustment coefficients are negative suggesting movement towards the long-run equilibrium, neither α_{loil} or α_{lsugar} are statistically different from zero suggesting no long-run relationship between the two price series in sub-period 2. This is to be expected as the second sub-period covers the period immediately before and during the 2008 financial crash. During this time, commodity markets were particularly volatile and there was a lot of uncertainty. Due to this, should a crash occur again it could be suggested there may not be a significant long-run relationship between the two prices, though this could again also be due to the short amount of time since the introduction of FFV's in Brazil.

4.5.3 Sub-period 3

Sub-period 3 covers the period from week beginning 24th March 2010 to week beginning 2nd August 2017. Equations 9 and 10 describe the short-run dynamics and long-run relationship between the oil and sugar prices.

Equation 9

$$\Delta loil_t = -0.001 - 0.008(\Delta loil_{t-1} - 2.457\Delta lsugar_{t-1} - 2.968)$$

Equation 10

$$\Delta lsugar_t = -0.001 + 0.005(\Delta loil_{t-1} - 2.457\Delta lsugar_{t-1} - 2.968)$$

Table 10 – VECM results sub-period 3

Coefficients	Oil	Sugar
v	-0.001	-0.001
α	-0.008**	0.005
β	1.000	-2.457**
β_0	2.968	2.968

** $p < 0.05$. Source: own calculations in Stata

Table 10 summarises the resulting coefficients from the VECM estimation in sub-period 3. As the adjustment coefficient α_{loil} is both negative and statistically significant to the 5% level, it is implied there is a long-run relationship between the two prices, and the oil price adjusts at a speed of 0.8% per period towards the long-run equilibrium. It can also be inferred that the oil price tends towards equilibrium in $\frac{1}{\alpha_{loil}} \approx 127$ steps, all else equal. This is a relatively long amount of time (almost 2.5 years) compared to some of the other sub-periods. This longer period of market adjustment could be due to the ongoing impact of the 2008 financial crash and subsequent global recession where governments and investors were more conservative and so not reacting as quickly to changes in prices.

However, only the adjustment coefficient on the oil price is statistically significant which could suggest only changes in the oil price have a significant impact on the long-run equilibrium between the sugar and oil prices. This could imply the oil price has more importance than the sugar price in determining their long-run relationship,

which backs up the existing literature ((Balcombe & Rapsomanikis, 2008), (Chen & Saghaian, 2015), (Chaudhuri, 2001)).

Equation 11 – Cointegrating equation

$$\Delta loil_{t-1} - 2.457\Delta lsugar_{t-1} - 2.968 = 0$$

Due to the significance on α_{loil} , we can estimate the cointegrating Equation 11. Based on this, it is implied there is a statistically significant strongly negative relationship between the sugar and oil price in the long-run, with a 1% increase in the sugar price being associated with a 2.46% decrease in the oil price in this sub-period, all else equal.

4.5.4 Sub-period 4

Sub-period 4 covers the period from week beginning 9th August 2017 to week beginning 3rd February 2023. Equations 12 and 13 describe the short-run dynamics and long-run relationship between the oil and sugar prices.

Equation 12

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta loil_t = & 0.187\Delta loil_{t-1} - 0.119\Delta loil_{t-2} + 0.127\Delta loil_{t-3} + 0.034\Delta lsugar_{t-1} \\ & + 0.135\Delta lsugar_{t-2} - 0.017\Delta lsugar_{t-3} \\ & - 0.037(\Delta loil_{t-1} - 0.924\Delta lsugar_{t-1} - 1.667) \end{aligned}$$

Equation 13

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta lsugar_t = & 0.002 - 0.008\Delta loil_{t-1} + 0.076\Delta loil_{t-2} - 0.038\Delta loil_{t-3} \\ & + 0.062\Delta lsugar_{t-1} - 0.058\Delta lsugar_{t-2} - 0.062\Delta lsugar_{t-3} \\ & + 0.003(\Delta loil_{t-1} - 0.924\Delta lsugar_{t-1} - 1.667) \end{aligned}$$

Table 11 – VECM results sub-period 4

Coefficients	Oil	Sugar
v	0.000	0.002
γ_1	0.187***	0.034
γ_2	-0.119*	0.135
γ_3	0.127**	-0.017
θ_1	-0.008	0.062
θ_2	0.076**	-0.058
θ_3	-0.038	-0.062
α	-0.037**	0.003

β	1.000	-0.924**
β_0	-1.667	-1.667

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$. Source: own calculations

in Stata

Note: the constant ν has been rounded down to 0 for the oil equation as extremely small value.

Table 11 summarises the resulting coefficients from the VECM estimation in sub-period 4. As the adjustment coefficient α_{oil} is both negative and statistically significant to the 5% level, there is implied a long-run relationship between the two prices, and the oil price adjusts at a speed of 3.7% per period towards the long-run equilibrium.

Despite the major oil price volatility during this sub-period, the adjustment coefficient on the oil price is relatively large with the oil price adjusting towards the equilibrium after $\frac{1}{\alpha_{oil}} \approx 27$ steps, all else equal. This could be due major global events causing oil price volatility; the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 caused periods of low demand for oil due to lower global production of goods, as well as substantially reduced travel both within and between countries. This low demand saw the price of oil drop, even becoming negative at one point. In February 2022, the Russian invasion on Ukraine combined with OPEC's decision to withhold oil supply saw oil supply drastically reduce which forced the price up to levels not seen since the 2008 financial crash, see Figure 1. However, due to these events being sudden and widespread, the prices adjusted particularly quickly in response, which could explain why adjustment is only in 27 steps as compared to the 127 in the previous sub-period.

As suggested in the previous sub-period, because only the oil price has a statistically significant adjustment coefficient, it can be proposed that only changes in the oil price have a significant impact on the long-run equilibrium between the sugar and oil prices. This suggests it is only in the past 14 years that the changes in the oil price impact sugar prices, 6 years after flex-fuel vehicles were introduced in Brazil.

Equation 14 – Cointegrating equation

$$\Delta oil_{t-1} - 0.924\Delta sugar_{t-1} - 1.667 = 0$$

Based on the cointegrating equation 14, it is suggested there is a statistically significant negative relationship between the sugar and oil price in the long-run, with a 1%

increase in the sugar price being associated with a 0.92% decrease in the oil price in this sub-period, all else equal.

The following chapter summarises the results above and concludes the dissertation.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

This dissertation has focussed on the long-run interactions, and how these have changed, between the sugar and the oil price given their relevance to each other following the introduction of flex-fuel vehicles (FFV) in Brazil in 2003. Current literature on the topic often researches the interactions between the sugar, ethanol, and oil prices using vector error correction models (VECM) and conclude with the oil price having a larger impact on the relationships compared to the other commodities (Balcombe & Rapsomanikis, 2008), (Carpio, 2019), and (Chen & Saghaian, 2015). I instead focussed more on the simpler interaction between the sugar and oil price as these are the main inputs for ethanol and gasoline, respectively. I expanded on previous literature by investigating how the relationship between the two has changed over different sub-periods. The use of structural break testing and subsequent division of the price series into sub-periods allowed me to bypass the need for a threshold vector error correction model while also providing an insight into how different global events might have impacted the long-run relationship between the two price series.

The analysis allowed me to split the data into four sub-periods, within which cointegration was found between the sugar and oil price, so a VECM was used to assess the long-run equilibrium relationship. The subsequent VECM's in each period only found statistically significant evidence of a long-run relationship in the third and fourth periods, covering the periods March 2010 to August 2017 and August 2017 to February 2023, respectively. The adjustment coefficients in these periods were statistically significant on the oil price equation only suggesting that changes in the oil price have a larger and more significant impact on the long-run equilibrium relationship than changes in the sugar price. These findings support existing research by Chaudhuri (2001), Balcombe & Rapsomanikis (2008), and Chen & Saghaian (2015), with Chen & Saghaian (2015) specifically only finding a long-run relationship in their second period from 2008 to 2014. Additionally, the speed of adjustment was notably longer in the third than the fourth period, 127 steps compared to 27, possibly due to the global scale

of events impacting the oil price causing prices to adjust more quickly in response during the fourth period.

The findings of a long-run relationship in the third and fourth periods only suggest that since the introduction of FFV's in Brazil, the interactions between world sugar and oil prices have become more closely linked and that, as other countries such as start to introduce similar schemes such as India's "Roadmap for Ethanol Blending" (International Energy Agency, 2023), the prices may begin to follow each other even more closely. This suggests that a large event impacting the oil industry might have an indirect impact on sugar prices, with other factors - such as how widespread the event is - determining the speed of adjustment back to equilibrium. On the other hand, an event solely impacting the sugar industry, such as localised weather events, might not impact the oil market to the same extent. These findings are useful for investors and policymakers in both markets as it can help inform of the consequences of potential policy decisions regarding renewable fuel sources and so allow investors to alter investment strategies to hedge against potential negative impacts.

Future research on this topic could extend the time period to explore the long-run impact of more recent events which have affected the oil price, for example the Russian invasion of Ukraine and the COVID-19 pandemic. In addition, further econometric techniques could be used to investigate deeper the relationship between the sugar and oil prices, such as Granger causality and impulse response functions, to confirm directions of causality to better inform policy makers and investors. Alongside this, my dissertation solely explores sugar and oil prices; to further understand why the relationship has changed, other factors such as climate data or levels of production could be studied to find potential causation.

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